

NARRATIVE IN SATISH ALEKAR'S *THE DREAD DEPARTURE*

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ABSTRACT

Narrative is generally not associated with drama as it tends to be more performative than other genres. But Indian plays have narrative as their essential element for they are mostly based on myths, folktales, history and Puranas. So Indian dramatists employ different narrative strategies such as characters as storytellers, retrospection, reporting, choric commentary, announcements, descriptions, thoughts, summaries, overheard conversations, letters, phone calls, Sutradharas, and confessions to name a few. Alekar has used narrative in Mahanirvan or The Dread Departure (1974). He has used two separate narrators for two Acts of the play to present the event of Bhaurao's death through different points of view. Their narrative styles change as their attitude towards the death. The paper tries to examine how narrative is employed to represent the central event of Bhaurao's death in Mahanirvan.

Keywords: Narrative, Point Of View, Focalization, Indian Drama, Paradigmatic And Syntagmatic.

Narrative is generally considered to be the basis of novel and interaction as the basis of drama. However, a drama too contains a story which is told through different modes, narrative is one of them. So dramatists exploit narrative techniques to tell their stories. That does not mean characters address the audience directly as narrators do in fictions. In some plays, we have the messenger, the Stage Manager, or the Sutradhara or the Bhagavata narrator narrating and mediating the action of the play. But mostly the character turns storytellers in their dialogues. In a play, narrative has many functions such as reporting, commenting, expositing, sermonizing, mediating, contemplating, retrospectively etc. According to Sisir Kumar Das, *the dramatic text can be treated as a narrative and narrative acts as its natural components. Still these components would gain their legitimate place in the dramatic text only when they aspire to the condition of enactment since the drama acquires its complete meaning through enactments (Das: 310).*

The narrative in drama has its source in myths, legends, *Puranas*, folklores, history, and epics. The kind of narrative these sources contain is not lost in their transposition into drama

but takes completely new form. The dramatist has to employ and manipulate different narrative strategies, like characters as storytellers, retrospection, reporting, choric commentary, announcements, descriptions, thoughts, summaries, overheard conversations, letters, phone calls, *Sutradharas*, and confessions to name a few. According to Nemichandra Jain:

...the narrative in a play is more than mere story-telling, a kind of score for visual enactment of the physical, mental, emotional activity inherent in the story or the episodes. Consequently, the emphasis shifts from description to presentation, and this tends to change completely the balance and relationships between various elements of the narrative-the incidents, situations, characters, the temporal and spatial sequences as well as the cause-effect conjunctions (p. 303-04).

The presence of narrative in drama affects its structure and relationship between its constituent elements. In order to incorporate narrative, a playwright has to employ various strategies such as exposition, retrospection, reporting, choric characters, *Sutradhara*, Character- narrators, dreams, framing narrative etc.

Indian dramatists make use of narrative very effectively. Narrative seems to be an essential element of their plays as they are mostly based on myths, folktales, history and Puranas. Girish Karnad, Dharmaveer Bharati, Badal Sircar, Ratan Thiyam, Sriranga and K. N. Pannikar have used narrative extensively in their plays. Satish Alekar and Vijay Tendulkar have used narrative in some of their plays. For example, Vijay Tendulkar's *Ghashiram Kotwal* (1972) and *A Friend's Story* (1975) and Alekar's *Mahanirvan (The Dear Departed)* (1974) and *Begum Barve* (1979).

This paper aims at analyzing the different points of view employed in the play and their implications. There are two different narrators for the two Acts of the play. Bhaurao, the central figure in the play, narrates the tale of his death and his past in the first Act. Nana, his son, takes over the narrative and presents the aftermath of Bhaurao's death till the last rite in the second Act. So how this change in the narrator has an impact on the structure of the play needs to be analyzed.

Mahanirvan or *The Dread Departure* was written in 1974 for Theatre Academy, Pune for the Maharashtra State Drama Competition. It was directed by Alekar himself and was performed at the Bharat Natya Mandir, Pune on 22 November, 1974. Chandrakant Kale played the role of Bhaurao and Nana was played by Satish Alekar.

The central event in *Mahanirvan* is the demise of Bhaurao, a very ordinary middle-aged man living an ordinary life in a chawl in Pune city. Normally such death would have been followed by gathering of related people and funeral rituals. Then the tenth and thirteenth day rites would have been performed according to Hindu religion. But in Bhaurao's case, there occurs some problems in conducting these rituals as the old crematorium was closed. So also Bhaurao's spirit did not free itself from earthly attachments and refused to be burnt in the new crematorium. So Nana, his son, takes the body home and put it in the loft as he decides to dispose the body after conducting the last rites of his father. The play is humorous rendering of what happens after the death of Bhaurao.

In the first Act, Bhaurao dons the mantle of a keertankar and comments on the events following his death that sets the bizarre tone. In the second Act, Nana becomes the narrator. He recites a stanza from the *Pasayadan* from the Dnyaneshwari, Saint Dnyaneshwar's commentary on the Gita and then moves on to narrate the incidents. Shanta Gokhale comments:

Alekar draws on many registers for his characters' speech, from the contemporary colloquial, to the old-style literary, choosing his register to underline the absurdity of a situation or a stance rather than to delineate character. Nana varies his speech from colloquial to historical to colloquial (Gokhale: 257).

The play begins with the central event, that is, the death of Bhaurao who is lying on the floor. His wife, Rama, is not ready to accept that her husband has died. When she gets convinced about the death, she calls their neighbours. Neighbours gather and start the preparation of Bhaurao's last rites. Then Bhaurao impersonates himself as keertankar and presents the fate of human body after death in a keertan style narration. After the funeral only bones of the body remain which are collected in an urn.

***Bhaurao:** As from trees the fruit and cones,
So hangs the flesh from your bones,
Just as the tree is dearly beloved, valued for the fruit it gives,
so your bones are enhanced by the skin that covers them.
What is this body all about but the flesh, and the bones?
For once you are dead and gone.
Then comes the time of the bone. The bone then that is
borne in your arms in an urn! Yes, in your arms, my dears, the
bone that is borne in an urn! And all that's left for now is your
rotting flesh and the Name. The Name of Rama that saw you
through all your life to this end!
So say: Rama, Rama, Rama, Rama, Rama
Seetarama, Seetarama (The Dear Departed:6).*

Bhaurao relates his own *katha* (story) in the keertan. He tells that he meets his ends in the prime of his life. One can share sorrow when one is alive but after death one has to bear it only. No one care for the sorrow of the dead. So the dead should be cremated to liberate his soul. He has a son called Nana, who is a very nice person. But unfortunately he was not present when his father died. His mother, Rama, was only present. She was also not able to accept his death. She fainted to know that he was dead. She cried hard. Nana should have been around to help her. He thinks about her after his death. She took care of him when he was alive. Now he is worried about her. She is the fairest woman on the block. So she attracts men in the neighbourhood. He is more worried because of this fact. Neighbours come to make her realise that she is a widow now and she has to take care of herself. Bhaurao relates his death:

That's how I died. A good man called Bhaurao was cut off in the prime of his life. When you're alive your sorrows are for sharing. But when you are dead they are only for bearing....in our little house, there are at the moment just the

two of us – and the only bringer of money is our son, our Nana, and he – let me tell you. He is such a son! Amongst the sons of men will live his fame echoing through earth-heaven-hell! But this is crisis day, I've left my life half-way and our flags are at half-mast and this son, our Nana, is not here alas! He is away on this most dire day. Only SHE is at home (9).

Bhaurao describes his son, Nana as a smart fellow. He was a great athlete. He went on to play Prisoner's base. He was on town's team. He was an obstinate child and must always get what he wanted. He also fulfilled Nana's desire as it was their ancient tradition. He says:

In the Ramayana, Rama demanded the moon and though it took this century to really fulfil his want, his smart mother showed him the moon in a mirror and satisfied him.... so also runs poor Ashwatthama's story who wanted milk and his mother gave him only water floury. And the poor boy with a sad face downed the cup, thinking perhaps of the baby-food to come.

Anyway. But our Nana was ever the smartest. He decided to follow where Rama and Ashwatthama led....So one day: When in famine this great land had dried out Nana made up his mind and cried out,

I will NOT, I tell you, I will NOT

Stop crying till you get me an APRICOT.

Now Where was I going to get an apricot? No one had anything of the sort! But he would not stop crying, so I asked him: Son, have you ever in your life seen one? He said, no indeed, and his mother, too, agreed. So I was free to cheat him, like tradition has decreed, I mean! And I went. Went hastening to the market and brought for him a lovely date. And thus I brought and fed him the dates and he laughed and was pleased, the innocent!That's Nana's story and Rama's and, of course, mine too (11).

After the arrival of Nana, the final procession begins. When the procession reaches the crematorium, they come to know that the old crematorium has been closed and a brand new crematorium is built, neighbours leave Nana with the body and go home. As Nana does not know what to do, he looks back to see his father talking to him. Bhaurao does not want to be cremated in the new crematorium. Hence, Nana has to take the body home.

In Act II, Nana takes over the legacy of Bhaurao and becomes the narrator. He is worried about his mother who has been sobbing since his father's death. He requests her to start the fire as he has to manage food at the eatery across the street or with food given by neighbours. It is the tenth day and prepare rice balls for the pallbearers. His mother is not getting up so he decides to sing a song to arouse her. He continues to tell the tale of Bhaurao but in a different style unlike his father's keertan style. The song has a desired effect and Rama starts cooking the rice. Nana is worried about the funeral of Bhaurao as the latter wants to be cremated in the old crematorium only. Bhaurao has fond memories of the old crematorium and he hates himself to be cremated anywhere else. He recalls:

A real crematorium is the one where you feel the ashes of your forefathers under your body as you lie on the pyre. The Shankar temple in front. The sulking Nandi. Vithoba next door. The devotional prayers of a morning. The

river that flows by. The Maruti temple just behind and Rama beyond that. You should have seen this anorexic river in the rains... That's my crematorium. I don't want to be ignited in a silicon oven that the corporation has built after inviting sealed tenders... this new place is for you, not for me (38).

As Nana is facing this problem, his mother starts dreaming about another man. She saw a man in a suit wearing glasses. She thinks that he fits into the frame she has been dreaming of for long time. Nana too decides to find out the identity of the person. When she informs him that the man was present at the time of funeral and was one of the pall bearers, Nana asks other pallbearers about him. But he could not identify that man. Then he decides to put Bhaurao as the man before his mother. He tries to convince Bhaurao to become that man:

The real reason we cannot find the third man is that he didn't turn up today. Even CIA won't be able to turn him up on the basis of available info. All mother remembers is a suit and a pair of dark glasses. She claims that she can't remember the face. Now let's try and get at the truth. We must not allow mother's frame to be empty. By hook or by crook we must arrive at the identity of that third from the left. And you can help me in that for you are going to be the third from the left. You said you appeared before her the last time as though in a dream. Now you can appear before her as you are. You can woo her. Wrap her around your little finger and finally make her admit to her part in your death. Who was this man? How did he manage to meet her behind your back? Did you know him before your death or is he more recent? And – and ... (55)

So Bhaurao becomes ready to play the man with dark glasses and dances with her.

In the meanwhile, Nana meets the keeper of the old crematorium and fixes Bhaurao's funeral through black market channel. Bhaurao is happy that his wish is being fulfilled. Bhaurao's uses the Keertan style narrative as

Wells, folks. Just a little more now; while you wait for the skull to break, let me finish this tale of ours. In these day even cremation is on the black market, but at least it is in the old place. So I am satisfied. Besides it was good exercise, walking to the pyre. Almost like a sati. My eyes are still cool because of the lumps of dough shading them. I see colours and many shapes and forms. Our block and our neighbours and Rama and her house and the thorny old frame of hers! And Nana, and the days before he was born. And yet I do not see it all because after all I am dead. You may remember how eager I was to be burnt! But now that I feel the flames I remember the old story of the mother-in law who decided to leave the household in the hands of her son's wife and go on a pilgrimage to Pandharpur (66).

While Nana and the watchman are waiting for the skull to break, Bhaurao makes his last wish. He wishes that his son should get water for bath when he returns home. Hence, his skull should break before the municipal corporation turns off the water supply for the day on the block. Nana too sees a girl sitting third from the left in the dress circle. She fills his empty frame. He likes her. The watchman announces the breaking of the skull. Nana asks for

cigarette to the watchman. The watchman gives him a cheap weed. Nana lights with his lighter and both exit in the opposite direction.

Alekar has used characters as narrators in *Mahanirvan*. So Bhaurao and Nana alternately play the role of narrator and character. Change in the focalization also brings about change in narrative technique and overall representation of action. Bhaurao uses traditional *keertan* style narrative to tell the story of his life and death. His is an objective commentary on life and death. Nana is a modernist and rationalist. He questions the rituals such as rice ball offering to Crows and other thirtieth day rituals. He does not mind his mother thinking of another man immediately after his father's death. Bhaurao takes over the narrative from Nana towards the end. The shift in narrative is obvious as Bhaurao uses parabolic narrative to express his feelings at his funeral.

Thus, the paradigmatic change in the narrator presents two different points of views on Bhaurao's death. The syntagmatic core features of narrative are Bhaurao's death, preparation of his last rite, Nana's arrival, closure of the old crematorium, Bhaurao's refusal for cremation at the new crematorium, the tenth and thirtieth day ritual, Rama's dreaming of the man, and Bhaurao's funeral at the old crematorium. The circular movement of narrative lends it an absurdist touch. Overall Alekar has succeeded in presenting the ordinary death of Bhaurao as an event to be celebrated through different focalizations. Narrative techniques such as character narrators, messengers, parables, keertan and songs have been effectively employed to examine Bhaurao's death on several levels ceremonial, psychological and social.

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